

Enhancing elementary EFL students' writing skills through interactive technology and task-based learning: A study with AhaSlides integration

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This study investigates the effects of integrating AhaSlides as an interactive tool with Task-Based Learning (TBL) on the writing skills of fifth-grade students in a private elementary school in Aceh Besar, Indonesia. Using a quasi-experimental design, 42 students ($N=42$) were divided into an experimental class ($n=21$) and a control class ($n=21$). Both groups completed pre- and post-tests assessing spelling, grammar, vocabulary, capitalization, and punctuation. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results showed that students taught with AhaSlides and TBL achieved significantly higher post-test scores than those in the control group across all writing components. *ANCOVA* confirmed that the experimental group outperformed the control group after controlling for pre-test differences. The intervention was particularly effective for lower-proficiency learners, helping reduce performance gaps. On the whole, the findings indicate that combining interactive technology with TBL can meaningfully enhance young EFL learners' basic writing proficiency.

Keywords: AhaSlides; Elementary Students; Interactive Technology; Task-Based Learning; Writing Skills

1. Introduction

Writing is the most challenging and complex of the four English language skills, especially in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) contexts (Phuket & Othman, 2015). Contrary to listening and speaking, which are learned by exposure, or reading, which involves primarily receptive processing, writing requires learners to produce, structure, and present ideas in an appropriate and proper form (Tosuncuoglu, 2018). This demands simultaneous mastery of organization, vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics, such as spelling, capitalization, and punctuation (Brown, 2001; Sukserm & Wasanasomsithi,

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2023). In young EFL learners, such demands are particularly hard to fulfill because they have to construct sentences in a non-native language not used for their daily conversation, when their cognitive and linguistic capacities are still underdeveloped (Viera, 2017). Next, writing is generally considered the most difficult skill to learn for Indonesian primary school students (Alisha et al., 2019).

Since Indonesia's independence in 1945, the national curriculum has undergone eleven revisions, the most recent being the Merdeka Curriculum (Alkampary et al., 2024). Along with these revisions, language policy changes have also reduced the role of English, especially after its removal from the elementary curriculum in 2013 (Rahmah & Qamariah, 2023). However, under *Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan, Kebudayaan, Riset, dan Teknologi Republik Indonesia Nomor 12 Tahun 2024*, English has been reintroduced and implemented from 2024 to 2027 as an optional subject and will become compulsory in 2027/2028. In this implementation, writing is emphasized as a key learning outcome for fifth- and sixth-grade students in Phase C. This is outlined in *Keputusan Kepala Badan Standar, Kurikulum, dan Asesmen Pendidikan Nomor 032/H/KR/2024*, which mandates that learners produce simple, structured texts and present them orally while developing coherence, writing conventions, phonetic awareness, vocabulary use, and strategies such as copying and using visuals, reflecting the writing sub-skills identified by Brown (2001).

Research on other EFL contexts indicates that students at this age range struggle to master their writing because they lack adequate exposure to actual use of English, insufficient teaching time, and the dominance of traditional modes of teaching that are very reliant on memorization (Abraham, 2015; Kusumawardhani, 2019). Conventional writing instruction tends to emphasize copying and controlled practice rather than authentic expression, resulting in students' inability to transfer knowledge into independent writing tasks (Ni'mah, 2016). This situation calls for innovative pedagogical approaches that not only strengthen linguistic accuracy but also foster learner engagement and motivation.

One promising approach is Task-Based Learning (TBL), which emphasizes the completion of authentic and meaningful tasks in the target language. TBL allows learners to apply English in authentic settings, promoting both fluency and accuracy. Research has established that TBL greatly enhances learners' writing ability through the improvement of vocabulary utilization, sentence structure, and text structure (Sari & Pangaribuan, 2018; Rivas & Cárdenas, 2024). In the educational setting of Indonesia, TBL has also been shown to generate motivation, creativity, and cooperative learning, which are central to the growth of young learners (Sitawati et al., 2022; Sholeh, 2023).

Aside from pedagogic improvements, the implementation of interactive technology has increasingly played a crucial role in supporting language acquisition. The ubiquitous nature of digital tools has transformed traditional classroom dynamics, enabling more student-driven and participatory learning spaces (Chapelle, 2017). Applications such as AhaSlides provide interactive features such as live quizzes, polls, and word clouds that not only engage the learners but also provide instant feedback. These are highly valuable in young learner classrooms, where attention and motivation are often a war to be fought and won (Romly et al., 2025). Although AhaSlides research in language acquisition is in its early stages, preliminary findings show that it can enhance learner motivation, engagement, and team interaction (Olena et al., 2023).

Despite the growing body of evidence concerning the efficacy of TBL and interactive technology, few studies have sought to examine their combined impact on young EFL learners' writing development. Most of the research on technology-enhanced learning has focused on adult learners or other skills other than writing (Golonka et al., 2014). In Indonesian primary schools, there is also a gap that can be observed, with empirical research on applying technology with communicative instruction still lacking. Addressing this gap is necessary since the effectiveness of English teaching at the primary level will prepare students for subsequent language study in later grades.

Therefore, this research aims to investigate the impact of the application of AhaSlides and Task-Based Learning on improving fifth-grade Indonesian EFL learners' basic writing skills. It specifically targets the sentence level, where young learners begin to form grammatically correct and meaningful sentences. At this stage, writing instruction centers on vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics as the foundation of higher-level skills. The question under investigation is the following:

- Is there any significant improvement in fifth-grade students' writing skills after they are taught using AhaSlides and Task-Based Learning?

This research holds significant value for both educators and policymakers in the field of elementary English language education, particularly in Aceh Province. By investigating the impact of integrating interactive technology (AhaSlides) and the Task-Based Learning method, the study aims to provide evidence on how these innovative teaching methods can enhance basic English writing skills among young learners. Understanding the effectiveness of these methods will contribute to the development of more effective and engaging teaching strategies appropriate to the learning needs of elementary students. The findings may also serve as a foundation for further research and innovation in technology-enhanced language education.

2. Background

2.1. The importance of writing proficiency in primary EFL instruction

Writing is widely regarded as the most difficult and demanding of the four language skills, particularly in EFL settings (Alavi & Salmani Nodoushan, 2004; Bektas-Cetinkaya, 2020; Birjandi et al., 2004; Choudhury, 2013; Salmani Nodoushan, 2007b, 2007c, 2009, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2023; Spanou & Zafiri, 2019; Svensson, 2018; Yusuf et al., 2021). Unlike listening or reading, writing requires learners not only to generate ideas but also to organize them and express them in a logical order, while maintaining control over vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics (Sukserm & Wasanasomsithi, 2023). Various influences impact the writing skills of learners, ranging from internal variables such as motivation and confidence to external variables including the learning environment and instructional methods (Budjalemba & Listyani, 2020).

According to Brown (2001), there are five important components of writing that are necessary for efficient written communication, especially while learning a second or foreign language. In EFL contexts, these elements (i.e., content, organization, vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics) provide a framework for evaluating and enhancing writing. Content refers to the clarity, development, and relevance of ideas; organization deals with the logical flow and structure of writing; vocabulary relates to appropriate and varied word choice; grammar guarantees accuracy through proper sentence structure and syntax; and mechanics involves technical correctness in punctuation, capitalization, and spelling. These elements work together to produce writing that is effective, logical, and clear. In addition, Kelly (2013) also outlines four stages of development in EFL writing, progressing from the word level to the sentence level, then to the composition level, and finally to professional or academic writing.

In teaching young learners, writing instruction requires interactive and child-centered strategies. Paul (2003) emphasizes that writing instruction should be integrated into daily lessons and supported by phonics-based work, games, and scaffolding cues. Similarly, Bourke (2006) argues that initial writing lessons should focus on primary skills such as handwriting, copying, and constructing short sentences before progressing to longer texts. Through scaffolding activities and striking a balance between accuracy and creativity, teachers can make writing both an engaging and productive exercise for children.

2.2. Task-based learning (TBL) in EFL contexts

Task-Based Learning (TBL) is communicative language teaching that focuses on engaging learners in meaningful, real-life tasks rather than simply focusing

on the form of language (Ellis, 2003; Giofré, 2026; Salmani Nodoushan, 2008; Weigand, 2018). The major idea is that learning language works best when learners use language as a tool to accomplish valuable outcomes. TBL typically has three stages: pre-task, in which students prepare; task cycle, in which students co-operatively work together to complete the task; and post-task, involving reflection and feedback (Ellis, 2017).

Extensive research supports TBL's positive effect on language learners' writing development (Gonzalez & Pinzon, 2019; Kaharuddin et al., 2022). With the inclusion of vocabulary and grammar practice within real communicative tasks, TBL builds both accuracy and fluency (Gonzalez & Pinzon, 2019). Sari and Pangaribuan (2018) reported that improvements were observed in Indonesian classroom academic writing when task-based activities were incorporated, noting improvements in coherence and grammatical correctness. In vocational and secondary education classrooms, Rivas and Cárdenas (2024) noted TBL to be effective in enhancing vocabulary usage, sentence construction, and overall quality of composition.

Interestingly, TBL activates creativity, problem-solving, and social communication skills required for young learners' social and linguistic growth (Chen, 2023; Sitawati et al., 2022). Tasks such as storytelling, information-gap activities, and collaborative project work build these skills while placing language learning in meaningful, achievable objectives. Persistence and effort, which are keys to skill mastery, are promoted by this activity (Shintani, 2014). Furthermore, TBL also provides considerable room for scaffolded support and peer feedback, both of which are critical in handling the wide spectrum of learner proficiency common in primary school classrooms. Long (2014) emphasizes that integrating explicit attention to language forms within communicative tasks allows learners to develop grammatical accuracy while still achieving meaningful communication. The methodology is thus aligned with the developmental requirements and cognitive capabilities of young EFL learners.

2.3. The use of interactive technology in language learning

The rapid development of technology has had a substantial influence on language instruction around the world, providing interactive tools that enhance learner involvement, motivation, and individualized learning processes (Chapelle, 2017). Ranging from gamified English language software to virtual reality systems, interactive resources for enhancing EFL reading, listening, speaking, and writing are gaining popularity. In the teaching of writing, technology allows for instant feedback, frequent practice, and use of authentic linguistic models, which enable the acquisition of skills (Golonka et al., 2014). For young children with short attention spans, computer-based

interactive materials combine aspects of game, competition, and visualization, stimulating interest and memorability (Zhang, 2024).

Applications such as Kahoot! and Quizizz have been empirically shown to be effective in memorizing vocabulary and grammar by way of quizzes and games, as well as to facilitate collaborative learning (Göksün & Gürsoy, 2019). Applications that enable mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) offer mobility and personalized pacing demanded by different learner profiles (Stockwell, 2022). Furthermore, interactive tools can improve reading, writing, speaking, and listening. VR and gamified apps particularly support speaking fluency and confidence (Ali, 2022). Platforms like Quizizz and Kahoot! encourage teamwork and peer interaction, essential for communication skill development (Inayati & Waloyo, 2022). These tools provide real-time feedback, helping students monitor progress and address weaknesses (Hori et al., 2024; Muchlis & Ardi, 2024). Moreover, the students' energy was transformed into a worthwhile educational experience by the online exercises, which also assisted them in connecting the concepts they had learnt in the computer lab to real-world situations (Ali, 2014). Furthermore, another study looked at how students' English skills are improved by technology-enhanced activities. The study, which used a qualitative action research design with sixth graders in a public school in Mexico, discovered that Edtech apps enhanced learning and speaking, writing, listening, and reading skills through interactive and gamified activities (Linares, 2024).

While these advantages exist, digital integration is challenged in EFL classrooms. These are the limits of infrastructure, unequal access to technology, the risk of distraction, and teachers' lack of training on technology-supported pedagogy (Ali, 2022; Sari, 2024). Effective use depends on strategic instructional design, technology alignment with learning outcomes, and continuing professional development to maximize its potential (Murthy et al., 2015).

2.4. AhaSlides as an interactive educational tool

AhaSlides was created in 2019 to make meetings, classrooms, public events, and quizzes more engaging and inspiring. It is an interactive presentation and audience engagement platform that allows educators to create stimulating and participatory learning experiences. It offers features that can be integrated into presentations (AhaSlides Pte Ltd., 2025). It is user-friendly and allows educators to create interactive presentations without extensive technical expertise. The platform supports integration with tools like PowerPoint, Google Slides, and Zoom, enabling educators to incorporate interactive elements into existing lesson plans.

There are several features offered by AhaSlides. First, Live Polls and Quizzes, which facilitate immediate feedback and assess student understanding in real-time. Second, Word Clouds, which visualize students' responses to open-ended questions, promote collective brainstorming (see Figure 1). Third, Q&A Sessions can encourage students' participation and address queries effectively. Finally, the Spinner Wheel introduces elements of gamification to maintain students' interest. These features support active learning strategies, making AhaSlides a valuable asset in ELT for enhancing student interaction and motivation. In addition, AhaSlides offers several benefits. It enables real-time interaction that encourages students to participate actively during lessons. It also provides a wide variety of question types, including multiple-choice, open-ended, and scale-based items. Teachers receive instant feedback, allowing them to quickly assess students' understanding. The platform includes gamification features, such as leaderboards and competitive elements, which help increase engagement. Moreover, it is highly accessible, as students can use it on various devices, including smartphones, tablets, and computers.

Figure 1.

Word Clouds (Brainstorming) Feature

AhaSlides and related tools have been studied recently for their potential to support interactive learning. Romly et al. (2025) and Achmad et al. (2025) discovered that AhaSlides successfully increased the motivation, engagement, and satisfaction of ESL learners. Similar findings were made by Berezina (2023), who highlighted the importance of tailoring digital tools to students' requirements and accessibility and found that AhaSlides, Flenga, and Wordwall enhanced classroom involvement through real-time assessment, feedback, and motivation.

3. Method

3.1. Research design

The present study used a quantitative paradigm that enhances systematic collection of data and statistical analysis based on numeric data to identify patterns, relationships, and causality with emphasis on objectivity and replicability (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Quasi-experiment was the research design utilized to examine the effect of applying AhaSlides and Task-Based Learning (TBL) on the writing skills of fifth-grade students of EFL. This design is applied where full randomization is impossible and allows comparison between an experiment and a control group (Kim & Clasing-Manquian, 2023).

3.2. Population and sample

The study was conducted in a private elementary school in Aceh Besar, a regency of Aceh Province in Indonesia. The population was 84 fifth-grade students. Two groups were randomly selected, and 42 students were considered the sample. Random sampling was applied to reduce selection bias and increase generalizability (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Fifth graders were chosen because they fall into Phase C of the Merdeka Curriculum and already have sufficient prior experience with English and IT. The experimental group learned with AhaSlides and TBL, whereas the control group learned without AhaSlides and TBL.

3.3. Research instrument

The test was used as the research instrument. The pre-test and post-test were given to the research participants to measure their writing skills related to creating simple English sentences. Vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics (spelling, capitalization, and punctuation) were assessed. Content validity of the instrument was maintained through expert evaluation and Content Validity Index (Heale & Twycross, 2015; Polit & Beck, 2006). Reliability was estimated through Cronbach's *Alpha* for internal consistency (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2009) and inter-rater reliability through Cohen's *Kappa* (McHugh, 2012).

3.4. Technique of data collection

The study was conducted over eight sessions in the odd semester of the 2025–2026 academic year. The first and final meetings were done for pre- and post-tests, and six sessions in between were given for treatment. Each session took 60 minutes to complete. The two groups used the same materials, and the topics were Giving Directions and Health and Sympathy. The students in the experimental group studied at the computer laboratory, where each student used a computer during the learning process. The laboratory also had a good

internet connection to connect with AhaSlides. The participants were taught by using the integration of AhaSlides and TBL. Conversely, the control group studied in the classroom using the traditional method used by the teacher (Fraenkel et al., 2012).

The data were analyzed descriptively (means and standard deviations) and inferentially (*t*-test and *ANCOVA*) for all variables by using *R*, a statistical tool. *T*-tests were utilized to compare pre-test and post-test scores within groups (Pallant, 2020), while *ANCOVA* was utilized to compare post-test scores between groups while adjusting for pre-test scores (Field, 2013). This allowed the researchers to determine the effect of AhaSlides and TBL on writing performance after adjusting for initial differences.

Ethical standards were guided by the 'do no harm' principle to ensure that participants were protected from any form of risk (Gullion, 2024; Hazari, 2023). Students and parents provided informed consent, and voluntary participation with the right to withdraw at any time was prioritized (Ajemba & Arene, 2022). Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained through the removal of personal identifiers (Cohen et al., 2017; Johnkenedy et al., 2023). Participants' dignity, welfare, and rights were respected throughout the research process (Fraenkel et al., 2012).

4. Results

This section discusses the results of the pre-test and post-test of control and experimental groups to find out whether any significant improvement in the basic writing skill of fifth-grade students who were taught using the integration of AhaSlides and TBL, and those who were not. Five aspects of the writing skill were measured: vocabulary, grammar, spelling, capitalization, and punctuation.

Table 1
Mean Score and Standard Deviation of the Control Class

Assessment Aspect	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Vocabulary	43.42	26.29	44.19	29.97
Grammar	39.28	22.36	42.50	30.06
Capitalization	17.85	15.29	43.33	35.26
Punctuation	0	0	43.33	35.82
Spelling	34.28	23.99	35.95	31.12

As for the control group, descriptive analysis of the pre-test and post-test scores shows an increase in the mean score for all components of writing ability, even though the control class did not receive special treatment but only

followed the conventional learning method. The mean and standard deviation for each component are shown in Table 1 (above).

From Table 1, in terms of vocabulary, the mean score (M) increased from 43.42 to 44.19, although with a relatively small increase. The standard deviation (SD) also rose from 26.29 to 29.97, indicating variation in ability among participants after regular learning. A similar increase occurred in the grammar aspect, with a mean score increase from 39.28 to 42.50 and an SD increase from 22.36 to 30.06. This indicates that regular learning continues to have some positive impact on grammar comprehension, even though the variation between participants has widened.

The capitalization aspect showed the most striking improvement, with the mean score increasing from 17.85 on the pre-test to 43.33 on the post-test, and the SD rising from 15.29 to 35.26. This improvement indicates that regular learning, even without additional treatment, is still able to strengthen 'some' participants' ability to use capital letters, possibly because this aspect is relatively easy to improve through repeated practice during writing activities.

A very significant change was also seen in the punctuation aspect, which in the pre-test received a score of zero and an SD of zero, indicating no measurable initial ability in the use of punctuation. After the regular learning process, the mean score increased to 43.33 with an SD of 35.82. This shows that conventional learning activities may still make a meaningful contribution to introducing and strengthening basic punctuation skills.

Meanwhile, the spelling aspect showed a moderate increase from a mean score of 34.28 to 35.95, with an SD that increased from 23.99 to 31.12. This increase is relatively small, indicating that spelling skills may require a more targeted learning approach to achieve more substantial improvements. The average values for each aspect can be seen more clearly in Figure 2.

Figure 2.

Interaction Plot of Pre-Test and Class on Post-Test

Overall, the results of this analysis show a positive trend in the improvement of writing skills among participants in the control class, even without any intervention or special treatment. The most notable improvement occurred in the capitalization and punctuation aspects, which may have been influenced by writing practice during the learning process. The increase in score variation in the post-test also indicates differences in the level of individual adaptation to the conventional learning methods used.

As for the experimental group, descriptive analysis of the pre-test and post-test scores in the experiment class shows a substantial improvement in all components of writing skills after the implementation of the learning intervention. These results suggest that the learning approach employed in the experimental class has a positive impact on enhancing students' writing skills. The mean and *SD* for each component are shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Mean Score and Standard Deviation of the Experiment Class.

Assessment Aspect	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Vocabulary	32.95	28.13	49.33	27.75
Grammar	36.19	25.78	46.42	27.25
Capitalization	18.80	19.16	63.33	30.83
Punctuation	4.52	20.73	79.76	25.32
Spelling	24.52	30.28	44.28	29.16

In terms of vocabulary, the mean score increased from 32.95 to 49.33 with a slight decrease in standard deviation from 28.13 to 27.75. This shows that the learning intervention not only improved participants' vocabulary skills but also helped reduce performance gaps among individuals. A somewhat similar improvement was seen in the grammar aspect, where the mean score increased from 36.19 to 46.42 with a decrease in *SD* from 25.78 to 27.25, indicating a general improvement in grammar mastery after intervention-based learning.

The capitalization aspect experienced a significant improvement, with the mean score rising from 18.80 to 63.33, and the *SD* increasing from 19.16 to 30.83. These results indicate that students gained a better understanding of capitalization, although the level of achievement still varied. The most notable improvement was found in the punctuation aspect, where the mean score jumped from 4.52 to 79.76 with an *SD* decreasing from 20.73 to 25.32. This change indicates that the learning strategies applied were very effective in improving punctuation skills, a skill that was relatively low before the intervention. In the spelling aspect, there was an increase in the mean score

from 24.52 to 44.28, with a slight decrease in *SD* from 30.28 to 29.16. This indicates an improvement in the ability to spell more accurately and consistently after the treatment was given.

Overall, these results confirm that the learning intervention applied to the experimental class significantly improved the writing skills of students in various aspects, especially in punctuation and capitalization. Consistent improvements in all components indicate that the methods used were able to strengthen the mechanical and linguistic understanding of participants, while also improving the consistency of performance between individuals in the writing process.

The paired sample *t*-test was also used to compare pre-test and post-test scores in each group to assess any improvement in writing skills after the learning process. In the control class, the analysis results showed an increase in the mean score from 27.0 on the pre-test to 41.86 on the post-test (see Figure 2 above), with the variance increasing from 249.36 to 843.02. The correlation value between data pairs of $r = 0.81$ indicates a strong positive relationship between the scores before and after learning. The *t*-test yielded $t = -3.65$ with a *p*-value of $0.0016 < 0.05$, indicating a statistically significant improvement in participants' writing skills even without special treatment. This improvement can be interpreted as the result of a routine learning process that continues to contribute to the development of basic writing skills.

Meanwhile, in the experimental class, a much more significant improvement was found. The mean score increased from 23.40 on the pre-test to 56.63 on the post-test, with the variance increasing from 495.43 to 651.86. The correlation between the paired scores of $r = 0.84$ indicates a very strong positive relationship between the pre- and post-treatment scores. The *t* value of -11.09 with $p < 0.001$ indicates a statistically significant improvement. These results confirm that the learning approach applied in the experimental class had a substantial impact on improving students' writing skills.

Overall, both groups showed an increase in scores after learning, but the size of the increase in the experimental class was much more noticeable than in the control class. These findings validate the effectiveness of innovative learning strategies in significantly improving writing skills compared to conventional learning methods.

A comparative analysis between the control and experimental groups was also conducted using an Independent Samples *t*-test after first ensuring that the assumption of variance homogeneity was met through Levene's Test. The results of Levene's Test on the pre-test data showed no significant difference in variance between the control and experimental groups ($F(1,40) = 0.26, p = 0.610$). Similar results were obtained in the post-test ($F(1,40) = 0.18, p =$

0.675). Thus, the assumption of variance homogeneity was met for both stages, allowing the analysis to proceed using a two-sample *t*-tests with equal variances assumed without violating the basic assumptions of parametric tests.

In the pre-test stage, the average score for the control group was 26.97 and for the experimental group was 23.40, with variances of 249.36 and 495.43, respectively. This indicates that the pre-test scores for the experimental class were slightly lower than those for the control class. The *t*-test results produced a statistical value of $t = 0.60$ with a two-tailed *p*-value of 0.552 (> 0.05), indicating that there was no significant difference between the two groups before treatment. Thus, the initial abilities of the participants in the control and experimental groups can be considered equivalent.

Conversely, in the post-test stage, the average score of the control group increased to 41.9, while the experimental group achieved 56.63, with variances of 843.02 and 651.86, respectively. The *t*-test results showed a *t* value of -1.75 with a one-tailed *p*-value of 0.043 (< 0.05), indicating a significant difference between the two groups after treatment. The experimental group showed higher post-test scores than the control group.

These findings indicate that the treatment given to the experimental group had a positive and significant impact on improving learning outcomes. Thus, the learning intervention implemented proved to be more effective than the conventional approach used in the control group, and contributed significantly to improving participants' understanding and performance.

Next, we performed an *ANCOVA* analysis on the data. Before performing covariance analysis on the data, tests were conducted on the main assumptions underlying the validity of the model, namely residual normality and homogeneity of variance between groups. The results of the residual normality test using the Shapiro–Wilk test showed a statistical value of $W = 0.97402$ with $p = 0.4461$. A *p*-value greater than 0.05 indicates that the residual distribution does not differ significantly from the normal distribution. Thus, the assumption of residual normality is fulfilled. Furthermore, the homogeneity of variance test using Levene's test produced a value of $F = 0.1767$ with $p = 0.6765$. This result shows that there is no significant difference in variance between treatment groups ($p > 0.05$), so the assumption of homogeneity of variance is fulfilled.

After ensuring that most of the basic assumptions were met, analysis of covariance (*ANCOVA*) was conducted to test the effect of treatment (class) on the post-test results by controlling for the effect of pre-test as a covariate. The results of the analysis showed that both the treatment variable and the covariate had a significant effect on post-test scores. The results can be seen in Table 3 (below).

Table 3
Results of ANCOVA of the Students' Post-Test Scores.

Source	<i>Df</i>	<i>Sum Sq.</i>	<i>Mean Sq.</i>	<i>F value</i>	<i>Pr.(>F)</i>
Treatment	1	1741	1741	8.009	0.007 **
Pre-test	1	20907	20907	96.182	<0.001 ***
Treatment: Pre-test	1	859	859	4286	0.045*
Residuals	38	7618	200		

Specifically, the *ANCOVA* test results indicate that the class factor has a significant effect on the post-test ($F = 8.683$; $p = 0.00546$), which indicates a difference in the average post-test scores between the treatment groups after controlling for the effect of the pre-test. These findings indicate that the intervention or learning conditions represented by the class factor had a real effect on improving participants' post-test results.

In addition, the pre-test covariate also showed a highly significant effect on the post-test ($F = 104.284$; $p < 0.001$). These results indicate a strong linear relationship between initial and final scores, whereby participants with higher Pre-test scores tended to obtain higher Post-test scores as well. Thus, Pre-test plays an important role as a predictor of post-test performance and is valid for use as a covariate in the model.

However, the results of the interaction between class and pre-test ($F = 4.286$; $p = 0.04528$) indicate differences in the slope of the regression line between groups. This means that the effect of pre-test on post-test is not uniform across all treatment groups. This condition indicates that the effect of treatment on post-test results depends on the initial ability level of participants. In this context, the effectiveness of treatment tends to vary according to each individual's pre-test level. This can be seen in Figure 2 (above).

Overall, these results reinforce the argument that treatment has a significant effect on improving learning outcomes, but the magnitude of the effect depends on the initial abilities of the participants. Thus, the *ANCOVA* model provides a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of the relationship between treatment variables, covariates, and learning outcomes, and emphasizes the importance of considering covariate interactions in evaluating the effectiveness of educational treatments.

5. Discussion

The findings indicate that integrating AhaSlides with Task-Based Learning (TBL) significantly enhanced the writing skills of fifth graders in vocabulary, grammar, capitalization, punctuation, and spelling. These findings contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the effectiveness of technology-enhanced task-based approaches in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teaching.

The significant vocabulary growth confirms earlier findings that digital materials and gamified websites assist young language learners in vocabulary acquisition (Golonka et al., 2014). AhaSlides' interactive features, such as quizzes and word clouds, enabled repeated exposure and instant feedback, which are two key conditions for word retention. This finding shows that the specifically applied intervention is able to have a greater impact on the improvement of vocabulary in the experimental group. This is in accordance with previous research, which states that learning using technology can improve the English vocabulary ability of young learners (Hazar, 2020; Laloan, 2022). TBL task practice offered situated models to reuse words through effective communication, arguing in favor of Ellis' (2003) view that learning vocabulary is optimally effective when embedded within authentic tasks.

The grammar development observed aligns with Shintani (2014), who found that technology-enhanced tasks facilitated grammatical correctness through practice, interaction, and instant corrective feedback. Unlike rote-practice-oriented methods, TBL's communicative focus placed grammar in context, while AhaSlides facilitated real-time input and corrective feedback. This supports Long's (2014) conclusion that blending communicative practice with attention to form facilitates equal development of fluency and accuracy.

The most dramatic improvements were in capitalization and punctuation, typically challenging aspects of EFL writing (Hyland, 2019), showing the most substantial improvement. The experimental group's sizable improvement attests to Al-Qaysi and Shabdin's (2016) finding that technology-oriented feedback mechanisms are effective in reducing learners' mechanical errors (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2007a, 2018). The aspects of capitalization and punctuation also became a focus in previous research because these aspects remain a challenge for students in writing (Nur'ainy et al., 2023). Therefore, digital support can help overcome this challenge (Ivanova et al., 2022). By embedding mechanical exercises in gamified activities, AhaSlides reduced boredom and increased motivation to focus on writing conventions.

For spelling, the experimental group improved significantly, consistent with previous studies showing that the use of technology can improve students' spelling ability (Lau Yen Yen et al., 2023). The interactive quizzes required students to pay attention to and self-correct errors, consistent with Swain's (2005) output hypothesis emphasizing the role of language production and thought in second language acquisition.

The *ANCOVA* results revealed that the intervention was highly beneficial for the students with lower initial proficiency levels, hence reducing achievement gaps versus traditional instruction. The result is consistent with Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, particularly the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) construct (Xi & Lantolf, 2021). With instant scaffolding and adaptive feedback,

AhaSlides ensured that the lower-proficiency students made progress as well, in line with previous research highlighting the equity benefit of technology-enhanced TBL (Sholeh et al., 2020).

These findings provide compelling evidence that the integration of interactive technology and TBL can boost critical aspects of writing and reduce achievement gaps. The findings are supported by recent research (Chen, 2023; Li, 2023; Mudinillah et al., 2024), which highlights the pedagogical potential of combining gamification and task-based pedagogy in classrooms for young learners.

6. Conclusion

This study confirms that integrating AhaSlides and Task-Based Learning effectively improves the writing skills of young learners within an Indonesian EFL context. Compared to traditional teaching, the experimental group demonstrated greater improvement in vocabulary, grammar, capitalization, punctuation, and spelling. Importantly, the intervention was particularly effective for lower-proficiency students, suggesting its potential to promote more equitable learning outcomes.

The study contributes to the literature by demonstrating how interactive technologies like AhaSlides can enhance TBL and enrich writing pedagogy in elementary schools. For teachers, the findings suggest that the integration of gamified, task-based digital activities can foster active participation and help students overcome entrenched issues in mechanics and grammar. For policymakers, the findings provide evidence that interactive technologies can support the goals of the Merdeka Curriculum by fostering active, student-centered learning.

Future research could extend these findings by examining long-term retention of writing skills, exploring teachers' implementation experiences, and piloting the method in diverse cultural and educational settings. Such studies would deepen understanding of how digital technology and TBL may be trained to more effectively access maximal potential in a range of EFL contexts.

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Authors' Statement

Diana Achmad contributed to conceptualization, research design, and data collection. Asnawi Muslem worked on data analysis and interpretation. Yunisrina Qismullah Yusuf assisted in the literature review, manuscript drafting, and final editing of the manuscript. Siti Sarah Fitriani contributed to the results and discussion, and proofreading.

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